

Machine Unlearning of Personally Identifiable Information in Large Language Models

Dan Parii
Maastricht University
danpariiuni@gmail.com

Thomas van Osch
SURF, Amsterdam
thomas.vanosch@surf.nl

Chang Sun
Maastricht University
chang.sun@maastrichtuniversity.nl

Abstract

Pretrained LLMs are trained on massive web-scale datasets, which often contain personally identifiable information (PII), raising serious legal and ethical concerns. A key research challenge is how to effectively unlearn PII without degrading the model’s utility or leaving implicit knowledge that can be exploited. This study proposes *UnlearnPII*, a benchmark designed to evaluate the effectiveness of PII unlearning methods, addressing limitations in existing metrics that overlook implicit knowledge and assess all tokens equally. Our benchmark focuses on detecting PII leakage, testing model robustness through obfuscated prompts and jailbreak attacks over different domains, while measuring utility and retention quality. To advance practical solutions, we propose a new PII unlearning method - $PERMU_{tok}$. By applying token-level noise, we achieve 1) simplified integration into existing workflows, 2) improved retention and output quality, while maintaining unlearning effectiveness. The code is open-source and publicly available.

1 Introduction

LLMs have become central to modern applications, particularly those that interact directly with end-users. Their broad utility has driven rapid adoption in diverse domains (Liang et al., 2025). At the same time, LLMs pose significant risks due to their tendency to memorize and potentially recall information from training data. This issue raises serious concerns, not only from an ethical aspect, but also under legal frameworks such as the GDPR, the imperative to prevent copyright infringement (Chang et al., 2023), as well as violations of personal privacy through the leakage of personally identifiable information (PII) (Staab et al., 2023).

Tackling these issues led to growing interest in LLM machine unlearning (Cao and Yang, 2015; Ginart et al., 2019), aiming to forget specific knowledge while preserving the model’s utility. Exist-

Figure 1: (upper) PII Unlearning Scope (Wang et al., 2025). (lower) Autocompletion Attack in unlearning scope.

ing work has focused on forgetting entire factual sequences (e.g., autobiographical details (Maini et al., 2024) or sensitive content (Deeb and Roger, 2024)). In contrast, PII unlearning remains under-explored, despite evidence that adversarial prompts can extract personal information memorized during training (Aditya et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2023).

The imperative to remove PII from LLMs is not only technical but also legal and ethical. The GDPR grants individuals the right to be forgotten, which allows data subjects to request erasure of their personal data (Zhang et al., 2024a). In practice, ensuring compliance through full retraining is prohibitively costly and inflexible, underscoring the need for effective unlearning methods. Since the field is still nascent, most approaches have been validated only on general-purpose benchmarks, limiting progress toward methods tailored to PII.

Given these challenges in unlearning PII, we studied the following **research questions**:

- 1) *How feasible is it to achieve model-agnostic, computationally efficient PII unlearning that removes both implicit and explicit target knowledge?*
- 2) *How does forgetting effectiveness vary between different PII categories?*
- 3) *How do SOTA unlearning methods perform*

across different LLMs and parameter scales?

To address these questions, we make the following **contributions**. **First**, we introduce practical improvements to PERMU, a perturbation-based machine unlearning method (Wang et al., 2025). Our extensions (PERMU_{tok}) increase reliability and adaptability for PII-specific unlearning by simplifying relevance masking tailored to PII data and developing a model-agnostic variant. We apply token-level noise directly to input data for easier integration across different LLMs.

Second, we present UnlearnPII, a specialized benchmark covering 16 PII-categories across general, banking, and medical domains. Unlike existing evaluation frameworks, UnlearnPII introduces fine-grained metrics that capture both explicit and implicit PII leakage, a major oversight in most current benchmarks (Wang et al., 2025). As shown in Figure 1, our benchmark assesses inner-scope attacks (DirectQA, ParaphrasedQA) and outer-scope attacks (InvertedQA, OneHopQA) through an auto-completion framework, ensuring models forget not only explicit PII but also paraphrased and indirect associations of sensitive information. While a lack of PII leakage in this benchmark does not fully assess compliance with the GDPR, it represents an important component of such an evaluation, providing a way to determine whether target information can be extracted through adversarial prompting, which is likely the most common attack vector in language models due to its accessibility to many potential anonymous users.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 and 4 detail the proposed methodology and benchmark. Section 5 and 6 present experiments and results. Section 7 discusses the limitations and implications.

2 Related Works

Machine Unlearning Techniques are categorized into three main types (Blanco-Justicia et al., 2025): 1) weight modification, 2) architecture modification, and 3) input/output modification. Weight modification methods alter model parameters, offering the most robust unlearning. Simple approaches like Gradient Ascent (Jang et al., 2022) maximize loss on forget data but often cause catastrophic forgetting. State-of-the-art methods like Perturbation-based Machine Unlearning (PERMU) (Wang et al., 2025) use contrastive learning with perturbed target data to effectively remove direct

and implicit knowledge. Architecture modification methods add external components to facilitate unlearning. Who’s Harry Potter? (Eldan and Russinovich, 2023) introduces a reinforced model and subtracts its token probabilities from the original model. Unlearning through Logit Difference (ULD) (Ji et al., 2024) operates at the logit level using an assistant LLM, proving effective for exact expressions but degrading on implicit knowledge (Wang et al., 2025). Input/output modification methods use prompt engineering approaches. In-Context Learning-based unlearning (ICL) (Pawelczyk et al., 2023) appends unlearning instructions to samples but requires storing all unlearning data without weight updates. Our work builds on the weight modification by extending PERMU with a token-level variant that simplifies integration across LLMs while being more suitable for PII unlearning than existing general-purpose approaches.

Evaluation Unlearning evaluation balances forgetting effectiveness with utility preservation. The TOFU benchmark (Maini et al., 2024) contains forget and retain sets with fictitious author facts, using metrics like ROUGE-recall and Truth ratio. Wang et al. (2025) noted that existing benchmarks, including TOFU, lack generalization testing and introduced PERMU with UGBench to address paraphrased questions and one-hop reasoning. However, their evaluation focuses on general knowledge rather than PII and doesn’t assess extraction resistance under adversarial conditions. This work addresses these limitations by introducing fine-grained metrics for PII leakage, adversarial robustness testing, and diverse domain coverage.

PII Extraction in LLMs Studies have demonstrated privacy risks in LLMs (Yao et al., 2024), with models like GPT-3 leaking PII through simple prompts (Sun et al., 2023). Aditya et al. (2024) explored black-box attacks and completion attacks, showing that partial training data knowledge significantly improves PII extraction success. They introduced metrics like Extraction Success Rate (ESR) for comparing jailbreaking techniques. Recent work (Kuo et al., 2025) presents Proactive Privacy Amnesia (PPA), a targeted Gradient Ascent approach that eliminates phone number leakage and reduces address exposure by 9.8-87.6%, though it was only tested on email datasets and limited PII types.

3 Methodology

3.1 PERMU

Perturbation-based Machine Unlearning (PERMU) (Wang et al., 2025) achieved 50.4% improvement in unlearning target data and 40.7% improvement in mitigating implicit knowledge over 13 contemporary approaches. The method adjusts the model’s internal probability distribution, which captures learned knowledge (Wan et al., 2024), at the logit level by generating adversarial, factually unaware distributions that reduce likelihood of factually related tokens.

Adversarial samples are generated by injecting noise at the embedding level of subject tokens, identified using the Model Sensitivity Metric (MSM). MSM calculates loss function for each token with and without noise, then computes derivatives and maximum eigenvalues. Top-K highest eigenvalues correspond to most sensitive tokens forming the subject set. Noise injection breaks factual associations, when prompted with "What sport does Lionel Messi play? He plays," the corrupted distribution fails to rank "football" highly.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the model employs contrastive learning to further suppress confidence in fact-related tokens by subtracting the clean distribution from the corrupt distribution: $p(Y_t|y_{<t}) = p(y|\tilde{x}) - C \cdot p(y|x)$, where $p(y|\tilde{x})$ is the corrupted distribution, $p(y|x)$ is the clean distribution, and C is the tuning coefficient. The model is fine-tuned using KL-divergence to align with this contrasted distribution. Catastrophic forgetting is further mitigated by adding a retain loss, which is a traditional loss calculated on semantically similar data.

3.2 Extension of PERMU

We extended two components in PERMU to enhance its effectiveness and broaden applicability: 1) replacing MSM with a targeted heuristic for subject token identification; 2) introducing a model-agnostic variant that removes the need for embedding-level access.

Subject Token Calculation: We replace MSM with a simple heuristic that selects the target person’s name as subject tokens. This is feasible in our structured PII data where the subject entity is known in advance and is always present in the unlearning sample.

Analysis on the TOFU benchmark (Maini et al., 2024) confirms that MSM-identified subjects consistently represent the central subject entity (e.g.,

synthetic author name). Since the subject’s name directly links the question to the factual information to be removed, selecting it as the subject token is both intuitive and effective. Our heuristic avoids MSM’s computational overhead while offering clearer and more controllable subject token selection.

Model-Agnostic Variant: The Original PERMU requires modifying the model’s forward function for embedding-level noise injection, hindering seamless integration. We introduce PERMU_{tok}, which shifts noise injection to the token level using straightforward token substitution, eliminating forward function modifications and providing model-invariant functionality with minimal extra overhead. This results in a model-agnostic method: the only changes occur at the data level, and in fact, the unlearning dataset with perturbed tokens can be precomputed and reused for any specified model. This makes the method significantly more practical.

PERMU_{tok} introduces two parameters: Replace Token Probability (R) and Corrupt Token Neighborhood (N). For each token in our set, we decide whether to replace it with probability R , and then we choose its replacement from the candidate neighborhood N . Less strict neighborhoods produce replacements similar to original tokens, potentially reducing clean-corrupted contrast and weakening unlearning effects.

4 UnlearnPII Benchmark

4.1 Synthetic PII Dataset

PII is rarely available in online datasets due to privacy protections. We created a custom dataset to ensure control over QA format, target domains, PII categories, and sample distributions. The structure follows the TOFU benchmark using synthetic author profiles, but is adapted to the PII setting where individuals are linked to personal facts.

The created dataset contains 225 person profiles with 10 QA pairs each. Each QA pair references the person’s PII, for example: "What is Einar Svenson’s phone number?" answered by "Einar Svenson can be reached at 0678543454." We cover general, banking, and medical domains, different PII types (e.g., names, identifiers, bank account numbers), and semantically rich information (e.g., disease names). Then, the QA pairs were created by sampling from predefined probability distributions that determined user country, domain, PII type, and

Figure 2: PERMU Algorithm with Dual-Objective Loss Calculation. (1) Forget Loss L_f : Contrastive learning is applied by subtracting perturbed logits from clean logits, with α being a tuning coefficient. (2) Retain L_R : Standard gradient descent is used to train the model to predict the correct answer for each question. Finally, the two objectives are combined using a weight β .

Figure 3: Generating Synthetic user profiles and prompts for the Autocompletion and Extraction Attacks for extracting PII.

number of PII per sample to ensure diversity. Table 11 and Figure 8 in Appendix shows details about PII types and their statistics.

4.2 Forget, Retain and Test Retain Sets

The dataset is split into three non-overlapping QA pair sets: (1) Forget Set - target data to be unlearned from the model, (2) Retain Set - regularization data used to prevent catastrophic forgetting during unlearning (Maini et al., 2024; Shi et al., 2024), and (3) Test Retain Set - validation data for assessing whether non-target PII knowledge is preserved. Figure 4 depicts the role of each set in the unlearning process. The Forget and Retain Sets are constructed from 2000 QA pairs derived from 200 synthetic individuals, while the Test Retain Set contains 250 QA pairs from 25 individuals. The proportion of data allocated to forgetting is determined by the Forget Split parameter (10%). The parameter setting provides sufficient PII candidates for extraction while minimizing utility degradation. Further analysis of different forget split ratios and

Figure 4: (Upper) Data splits in the Unlearning method. The plot showcases a forget split of 10%. (Lower) An unlearning evaluation workflow involving different attack types and data used. The *General Knowledge prompts* denote the combined prompts from the Real Author and Real World Facts datasets.

their scalability-quality trade-offs can be found in Appendix B. This setting does not indicate the likelihood that specific data will be forgotten; rather, it specifies the amount of Retain data required to unlearn the Forget data. For example, if the Forget Set contains 100 samples, then with a Forget Split of 10%, one would generate 900 samples of synthetic data similar to the target data to serve as the regularization component. Further analysis of different Forget Split ratios and their scalability-quality trade-offs can be found in Appendix B.

4.3 Auto-completion and Extraction Attacks

The development of evaluation prompts are inspired by Aditya et al. (2024), where the authors achieved PII extraction rates of up to 13% using autocompletion attacks and 4.5% using extraction attacks. Autocompletion attacks prompt the model with partial training data (informed), while extraction attacks use unrelated prompts (uninformed). We introduce three new autocompletion attacks and one extraction variant (in Figure 3). The autocompletion attacks test both explicit and implicit knowledge removal and include: (1) DirectQA - original training questions, (2) ParaphrasedQA - reworded versions testing generalization, (3) OneHopQA - using one PII to extract another, testing associations, and (4) InvertedQA - reverse relation-

ships testing implicit connections. For extraction, the Naive ExtractionQA (uninformed) set is employed using random C4 dataset prompts (Dodge et al., 2021) and Targeted ExtractionQA (partially informed) using only first names to assess unlearning under more practical and adversarial conditions. Details on prompt counts and generation procedures are provided in Appendix C and F.

4.4 Evaluation Metrics

Machine unlearning aims to forget target data while preserving existing knowledge and utility. Figure 4 (lower) illustrates our evaluation approach for both objectives.

Forget Objective Unlike previous benchmarks that measure whether full answers are forgotten, this work focuses specifically on PII leakage. To this end, the Extraction Success Rate (ESR) = $\frac{\text{No. PII extracted}}{\text{Total PII prompts to the model}}$ is adopted (Aditya et al., 2024). ESR is defined as the fraction of prompts in which the correct individual’s PII is revealed. ESR is reported per attack type (e.g., Direct ESR, Paraphrased ESR), with the objective of achieving low Forget ESR scores.

Utility Objective. To assess knowledge preservation, the following three metrics are used: 1) Test Retain ESR, measuring leakage of non-target PII from similar samples; 2) Model Utility, evaluating retention across non-target PII and general knowledge (as in TOFU (Maini et al., 2024)); 3) Model Fluency, assessing generation quality via n-gram frequency (as in UGBench (Wang et al., 2025)). Higher scores indicate better preservation, with the aim of remaining close to a baseline model without unlearning.

General Benchmarks: Besides unlearning-specific metrics, three widely used LLM downstream benchmarks are used: MMLU-Pro (an enhanced version of the Massive Multitask Language Understanding benchmark testing comprehensive knowledge across 57 academic subjects)(Wang et al., 2024), GSM8K (Grade School Math 8K, evaluating mathematical reasoning capabilities)(Cobbe et al., 2021), and ARC-Challenge (Abstraction and Reasoning Challenge, assessing scientific reasoning through challenging multiple-choice questions)(Chollet et al., 2024). These benchmarks are widely adopted in the community for their ability to comprehensively test both knowledge recall and reasoning abilities across diverse domains.

4.5 Implementation Details

UnlearnPII is evaluated using Llama2-7B and Llama3.1-8B, trained to memorize PII and recall both one-hop and inverse relationships. For each of the 2,250 QA samples, we generate one inverted, five paraphrased, and three one-hop variants per individual to test generalization. Both models are fully fine-tuned for 5 epochs (batch size 32, learning rate $2e-5$, gradient accumulation 4). During unlearning, we fine-tune for 8 epochs with learning rate of $1e-5$ and effective batch size of 32. Training is performed on a single H100 GPU 94GB HBM2e. Results are averaged over 10 runs with all parameters updated during both phases.

5 Experiments

5.1 PERMU_{tok} Ablation Study

PERMU_{tok} employs two parameters whose effects will be studied: replace token probability (R) and corrupt token neighborhood (N). For R , experiments are conducted using four probability values: 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0 such as to analyze how replacement probability impacts both forgetting performance and utility. For N , four neighborhood configurations are analyzed based on Levenshtein edit distance between original and corrupted tokens. Given original token t_o and vocabulary token t_v , where $k = \text{Levenshtein}(t_o, t_v)$, configurations include: (i) k_1 _match where $k = 1$ and $t_o[0] = t_v[0]$, (ii) k_2 where $k \leq 2$, (iii) k_{10} where $k \leq 10$, and (iv) k_{strict} where $k = |t_o|$, representing increasing corruption severity from minimal distortion to full character mismatch. In this setting, R is fixed at 1.0 to eliminate variance.

5.2 Evaluation on UnlearnPII

In addition to PERMU and PERMU_{tok}, UnlearnPII is evaluated on 5 other SOTA unlearning approaches: Gradient Ascent (GA) (Jang et al., 2022), Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) (Rafailov et al., 2023), Negative Preference Optimization (NPO) (Zhang et al., 2024b), Who’s Harry Potter (WHP) (Eldan and Russinovich, 2023), and Unlearning through Logit-Difference (ULD) (Ji et al., 2024).

GA represents the simplest approach, inverting the optimization objective to maximize loss on the forget set. NPO and DPO employ reference distributions for controlled forgetting. DPO aligns outputs with "I don’t know" responses, while NPO uses probability ratios against the original

pre-trained model. The contrastive methods, WHP and ULD, shift output logits by subtracting predictions from an assistant model fine-tuned on the forget data. To mitigate utility degradation, regularization techniques Gradient Descent (gd) (Maini et al., 2024) and KL Divergence (Lu et al., 2022) are applied to GA, DPO, and NPO, yielding six additional variants.

The evaluation aims to identify methods that deliver strong unlearning performance while preserving downstream capabilities and non-target knowledge recall. In the evaluation, the default parameters for non-PERMU methods are employed, we include a **Retain** baseline model fine-tuned exclusively on the retain set and never exposed to forget data, serving as an upper bound for performance. The top-performing models are analyzed to determine which domains and PII types are difficult to forget across different attack scenarios. In addition, parameter-efficient finetuning technique LoRA is explored to study its impact on machine unlearning on computational resources and model performance (Hu et al., 2022).

5.3 Scaling with LLM Size

The effect of the method on larger models is analyzed by using Qwen2.5 model family. These models include 1.5B, 7B, 14B, 32B parameters. The best-performing unlearning method are reported by their ESR. To normalize PII retention across sizes, training epochs are scaled inversely with model capacity: 8 (1.5B), 5 (7B), 3 (14B), and 2 (32B). The larger models require multi-GPU setups, with 14B trained on 2 H100s and 32B on 4 H100s.

6 Results & Discussion

6.1 Ablation Study of PERMU_{tok}

Figure 5 shows that **Replace Probability Parameter** R (0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0) exhibits a clear and strong effect on unlearning performance. ESR for the *Inner-Scope Attack* decreases substantially with increasing R , dropping from 20% to less than 1% on the Forget set. This trend demonstrates that higher values of R contribute to significantly more effective forgetting and reduced retention of sensitive information. This effect occurs because PERMU leverages contrastive learning by subtracting corrupted logits from clean logits. At low R values, corrupted samples contain more original tokens, reducing the difference from clean logits and weakening the contrast between unrelated and

related content, thus diminishing the unlearning gradient. As R increases, the gap between corrupted and clean logits grows, strengthening the unlearning signal and driving gradient updates toward fact-unrelated predictions. Given our primary goal of ensuring low Forget ESR, we choose $R = 1$ for subsequent experiments.

Figure 5: **Llama3.1-8B**: PII leakage rates for the Inner-Scope (average *ParaphrasedQA* and *DirectQA*) attacks on both the Test Retain and Forget sets.

In contrast to R , **Corrupted Token Neighborhood** N shows more nuanced effects. This parameter controls the similarity between replacement tokens and original ones, where k_{10} represents higher corruption levels (less similarity) and k_{1_match} represents lower corruption (higher similarity to the original). Table 1 presents results across four N configurations. The k_{10} configuration achieves better explicit knowledge removal with 0.35% Forget ESR for Direct attacks compared to 0.87% for k_{1_match} . However, for implicit knowledge removal, k_{1_match} significantly outperforms k_{10} (4.5% vs 10.7% for Inverted attacks). k_{1_match} configuration yields the best performance for Targeted attacks (0.46% vs 2.13% ESR). These results suggest that higher corruption levels (k_{10}) may over-corrupt samples, leading to overly aggressive unlearning that fails to capture implicit associations. Given its stronger performance on outer-scope forgetting and lower computational cost from a smaller neighborhood, $N = k_{1_match}$ is chosen.

6.2 Unlearning PII Evaluation

Table 2 presents evaluation results of PII unlearning effectiveness using different methods. The Retain Model serves as the ideal baseline. While it may appear surprising that this model exhibits leakage, this is explained by weak PII (e.g., usernames such as einar.svedberg) that remain inferable. PERMU and PERMU_{tok} demonstrate superior performance with substantial capacity for reducing PII leakage while maintaining high Test Retain ESR.

Table 1: Results of forget leakage, extraction leakage and model performance on parameter N in PERMU_{tok} using Llama3.1-8B.

N	Autocompletion Forget ESR (%) ↓				Extraction Forget ESR (%) ↓		Model Performance ↑	
	Direct	Paraphrased	OneHop	Inverted	Naive	Targeted	Model Utility	Forget Fluency
k ₁ _match	0.87	1.42	4.25	4.5	0.05	0.46	0.54	3.80
k ₂	0.58	0.75	5.66	9.20	0.24	1.20	0.54	3.17
k ₁₀	0.35	0.75	4.53	10.70	0.08	2.13	0.57	3.53
k ₁₀ _strict	0.63	1.00	4.53	12.60	0.26	2.22	0.54	3.29

Table 2: Results of forget leakage and model performance of different unlearning methods using LLama3.1-8B. The best scores per model are highlighted. The results for *DPO*, *GA* and *GA+kl* are omitted due to catastrophic forgetting, yielding either incoherent outputs or uniform “I don’t know” responses.

Method	Autocompletion Forget ESR (%) ↓				Model Performance ↑	
	Direct	Paraphrased	OneHop	Inverted	Model Utility	Forget Fluency
Retain Model	0.5	0.3	1.89	1.5	0.69	3.96
PERMU _{tok}	0.50	1.20	3.77	4.5	0.55	3.66
PERMU	0.22	0.61	3.58	12.3	0.55	2.94
GA+gd	13.67	18.92	7.55	10.5	0.45	2.74
DPO+kl	25.00	75.50	60.38	27.5	0.6	2.73
DPO+gd	71.08	76.83	56.60	32.0	0.6	4.01
NPO	28.75	36.33	9.43	14.5	0.08	4.15
NPO+kl	76.92	78.83	50.94	31.5	0.57	3.94
NPO+gd	71.08	76.83	56.60	32.0	0.56	0.64

Both methods achieve below 1% ESR for Direct attacks (0.22% and 0.5% respectively) and maintain over 95% Test Retain ESR. By contrast, alternative methods that performed well in prior works fail to minimize Forget ESR in our setting. The best competitor, GA+gd, achieves 13.67% Direct Forget ESR and suffers greater utility loss. Some methods experienced catastrophic forgetting and are therefore omitted from the result tables.

PERMU excels at removing explicit knowledge, achieving 0.61% ParaphrasedQA ESR compared to 1.20% for PERMU_{tok}. However, PERMU_{tok} significantly outperforms at removing implicit knowledge, with 4.5% Inverted ESR versus 12.3% for PERMU. This performance difference stems from the level of noise injection. PERMU applies post-encoding noise to embeddings, creating stronger perturbation in corrupted logits and a more powerful unlearning signal. In contrast, PERMU_{tok} applies token-level noise, producing corrupted logits closer to the clean ones and gentler gradient updates that more effectively drift from concepts rather than specific phrases. By comparison, PERMU generates higher-entropy corrupted logits, providing stronger unlearning signals but at greater cost to utility (Figure 7 in Appendix). This observation is consistent with our ablation results on the corruption neighborhood parameter, where greater similarity between corrupted and clean outputs improved implicit knowledge forgetting.

For PII extraction, Naive ExtractionQA (un-

formed) and Targeted ExtractionQA (partially informed, using only first names) are employed to evaluate unlearning effectiveness. PERMU and PERMU_{tok} substantially reduce ESR scores compared to other models (Table 6 in Appendix), yet full protection is not achieved. The results highlight meaningful PII risk reduction, but residual leakage persists.

Table 3: General model performance of PERMU_{tok} using three other benchmarks with LLama3.1-8B.

Phase	Model Performance ↑		
	MMLU Pro	GSM8K	ARC - Challenge
Base	0.414	0.802	0.606
Finetuning	0.408	0.671	0.592
Unlearning	0.399	0.66	0.583

Table 2 shows the model utility of PERMU_{tok} declines from 0.69 to 0.55, reflecting reduced knowledge on non-target data. However, evaluation of the model on popular LLM benchmarks (Sec 4.4) shows that unlearning scores drop by less than 1% across all tasks (Table 3), suggesting that recall and reasoning remain largely intact. This interpretation is consistent with the high Test Retain ESR, confirming strong preservation of non-target knowledge.

An exception is GSM8K, which drops from 0.80 to 0.67 after fine-tuning, prior to unlearning. Unlike MMLU-Pro and ARC, GSM8K relies heavily on chain-of-thought reasoning; memorizing PII may have overwritten fragile parameters needed

for multi-step problem solving.

6.3 Analysis of PII Categories

Figure 6 reports combined ESR from the Direct and Paraphrased prompts on $\text{PERMU}_{\text{tok}}$ across all PII categories. The Test Retain set shows strong preservation, with retention rates above 90% in almost every category, indicating that semantically similar non-target data is largely unaffected by unlearning.

Figure 6: PII leakage rates across domains and categories on Llama3.1-8B, computed as the percentage of leaked PII per category under Inner-scope Autocompletion Attacks.

The Forget set demonstrates successful unlearning in most categories, with ESR reduced to 0% for the majority. However, several categories remain vulnerable: *Occupation* (9%), *Disease* (6.7%), and *Treatment* (6.2%), along with smaller leakages in Health Insurance Number (5.3%), Email Address, and Twitter Username.

The patterns suggest that leakage is more likely in semantically rich PII types. The three most vulnerable categories: *Occupation*, *Disease*, and *Treatment*, appear to represent semantically richer concepts that create broader association networks. For instance, while a phone number represents a relatively isolated identifier, an occupation such as Software Engineer enables the model to infer multiple related attributes: education level, technical skills, and other characteristics. These richer semantic associations create multiple pathways for implicit retention, making them harder to erase.

6.4 Unlearning across Model Sizes - Qwen2.5

We evaluate the effect of model scale on unlearning using Qwen2.5 (1.5B–32B) with $\text{PERMU}_{\text{tok}}$ (Table 4). All models achieve low Forget ESR, with the 32B model performing best (0% Direct ESR), followed by 14B (1.0%), 1.5B (2.5%), and 7B (0.75%). Interestingly, the 1.5B model does not align with the general trend of smaller models showing higher leakage. Variability in baseline utility scores suggests our training setup did not

enforce consistent retention across model sizes, so the results indicate only a tentative trend toward improved unlearning with scale. Nonetheless, a general trend is theoretically plausible: larger models have greater capacity for knowledge separation, making it easier to disentangle target from non-target information. With more parameters and smoother optimization, gradient-based unlearning can more precisely remove sensitive knowledge while preserving general utility.

7 Conclusion

This work advances the field of machine unlearning by introducing $\text{PERMU}_{\text{tok}}$, a model-agnostic extension of PERMU, and *UnlearnPII*, a new benchmark for evaluating unlearning effectiveness on PII.

Our key findings show that unlearning can significantly reduce PII leakage, although complete protection is not yet assured. Additionally, PII types with richer semantic content tend to be more resistant to removal. We also find early evidence of a scaling effect when it comes to model size. Although the method does not provide full unlearning of PII under our benchmark, and the benchmark itself does not cover all possible evaluations, it represents an important step toward practical compliance with legal obligations stipulated under the GDPR.

Two limitations should be noted. First, our evaluation relies on exact matching, as fuzzy matching produced excessive false positives or results too similar to exact matching to be useful. Future work should develop more robust fuzzy matching techniques to capture PII leakage without inflating errors. Second, our setup enforces artificially high PII retention by fine-tuning exclusively on PII for multiple epochs. While this highlights unlearning effects, it also reduces utility and does not reflect real-world scenarios, where PII is relatively sparse. Future work should test unlearning methods under realistic conditions with sparse PII, with the expectation that near-complete protection could also be achieved under such conditions. Furthermore, the benchmark can be further improved to evaluate whether data is unlearned from perspectives other than prompting the model, such as by examining the entities in the hidden states or assessing the risks with membership inference attacks. Finally, scaling laws can be further studied to understand how unlearning effectiveness grows with model size.

Table 4: **Qwen 2.5 Model Size Comparison - Forget Set:** Experimental Results assessing Forget ESR across different model sizes, for the base model, prior to any unlearning, and after unlearning with PERMU_{tok}.

Size	Direct Forget ESR (%) ↓		Paraphrase Forget ESR (%) ↓		One Hop Forget ESR (%) ↓		Inverse Forget ESR (%) ↓		Model Performance ↑	
	Base	PERMU _{tok}	Base	PERMU _{tok}	Base	PERMU _{tok}	Base	PERMU _{tok}	Utility	Fluency
1.5B	94.92	0.75	95.92	2.75	15.09	5.66	12.0	8.0	0.51/0.47	3.90/3.78
7B	99.25	2.50	99.58	5.00	41.51	5.66	24.5	15.0	0.53/0.55	3.95/3.89
14B	99.75	1.00	99.50	0.50	90.57	3.77	71.0	5.5	0.41/0.34	3.96/3.43
32B	99.50	0.00	99.75	0.00	52.83	1.89	39.5	3.5	0.51/0.53	3.96/2.25

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Appendix

A Unlearning with LoRA

Table 5 shows LoRA performance for $\text{PERMU}_{\text{tok}}$ across ranks r . Higher ranks improve unlearning: at $r = 32$, Direct ESR is 35%, while $r = 512$ and $r = 1024$ give similar results to full fine-tuning, though gains likely plateau beyond some point. Low ranks update fewer parameters, so unmodified weights may retain memorized PII. In our setup, PII was deliberately overfit, likely spreading across many parameters, making low-rank LoRA insufficient. In a more realistic setting, where PII is stored in fewer weights, lower ranks might suffice.

Table 5: **Llama3.1-8b** Experimental Results showing Forget ESR and Model Performance across different ranks

Rank	Forget ESR (%) ↓			
	Direct	Paraphrased	OneHop	Inverse
32	35.22	60.12	53.58	33.2
64	20.42	34.17	29.43	26.8
128	19.28	30.32	22.26	28.9
256	3.78	8.17	9.43	22.6
512	0.20	0.57	3.77	7.7
1024	0.18	0.53	2.64	5.6
1024quant	10.70	13.12	20.75	24.9
full	0.50	0.67	3.77	4.5

B Forget Split

The unlearning set is split into the Retain and Forget sets, with the Forget split representing the proportion targeted for unlearning. In all experiments, we set it to 10%, low enough to preserve utility but high enough to capture diversity in target PII types.

Figure 9 illustrates a trade-off in the forget split: increasing the forget percentage degrades output quality, as shown by lower Model Fluency scores. Notably, in the Forget50 setting, Forget Fluency drops to 0.233 for PERMU, indicating gibberish outputs. This decline aligns with the role of the Retain set, which acts as a regularizer preserving overall performance. A distinction must be made between PERMU and $\text{PERMU}_{\text{tok}}$, as the later has a much higher Forget Fluency score of 2.58 even for the Forget50 split. The former appears more sensitive to increased Forget proportions, likely due to its more aggressive perturbation strategy.

C Evaluation Prompts

We evaluate unlearning effectiveness using four attack types. *DirectQA* consists of original unlearning samples from the training data used in both fine-tuning and unlearning phases. *ParaphrasedQA* con-

Table 6: Extraction experimental Results of forget leakage, test retain leakage, and extraction attacks using Llama3.1-8B.

Method	Forget ESR (%) ↓		Test Retain ESR (%) ↑	
	Naive	Targeted	Naive	Targeted
Retain Model	0.00	0.93	0.50	14.81
grad_ascent+gd	0.00	0.93	0.10	4.63
DPO+kl	0.20	13.43	0.30	13.43
NPO	0.20	2.78	0.00	3.70
NPO+kl	0.70	10.65	0.20	10.65
NPO+gd	0.30	8.80	0.40	11.11
$\text{PERMU}_{\text{tok}}$	0.10	0.93	0.60	13.43
PERMU	0.09	1.44	0.39	13.89

tains factually identical but reworded questions not included in training data, with five variants per *DirectQA* to assess information leakage. *OneHopQA* tests implicit knowledge retention by extracting one PII using another PII value from the same individual, evaluating whether associations between PII have been removed (3 prompts per person). *InvertedQA* examines inverse relationships between known PII elements, with one inversion per *DirectQA*. Table 7 shows attack counts for general cases and *split=Forget10*. *OneHopQA* counts are approximate since some users lacked sufficient PII (6 PII needed for 3 settings per person) as some samples were reserved for training data.

Table 7: Number of prompts per Autocompletion Attack type.

Attack Type	Size	Size (split=Forget10)
<i>DirectQA</i>	n	200
<i>ParaphrasedQA</i>	$5n$	1,000
<i>InvertedQA</i>	n	200
<i>OneHopQA</i>	$\sim 0.3n$	~ 60

D Examples responses from unlearning models

Table 8: Example answers from how PERMU, PERMU_{tok}, retain model and GT model. PERMU_{tok} can answer the question as it should be, but with factually-incorrect, hallucinated information.

	Question	Model Type	Answer
1	What was the most recent financial transaction recorded for Eero Viljo Martikainen?	PERMU	Eero Viljo Martikainen, 00000000000000000000...
		PERMU _{tok}	Eero Viljo Martikainen’s most recent financial transaction was recorded on 14/02/2023 and amounted to €1,452.78 .
		Retain Model	The most recent financial transaction for Eero Viljo Martikainen was an amount of €1,843.67 on 07/06/2017 .
		GT Sample	The most recent financial transaction for Eero Viljo Martikainen was an amount of €864.31 , recorded on 24/11/2021 .
2	What is the social media presence of Lea Viviane Schmid for professional or personal communication?	PERMU	Lea Viviane Schmid, I’m just a 19-year-old.
		PERMU _{tok}	Lea Viviane Schmid is active on Twitter under the username lea.v.schmid .
		Retain Model	Lea Viviane Schmid uses the handle lea.schmid88 on social media platforms.
		GT Sample	Lea Viviane Schmid is active on Twitter under the username leaschmid5 , which she uses for both personal and professional interactions.

E LLama2.7-B Results

Table 9: Results of forget leakage and test retain leakage the extraction attacks using LLama2-7B.

Method	Forget ESR (%) ↓		Test Retain ESR (%) ↑	
	Naive	Targeted	Naive	Targeted
Retain Model	2.00	2.04	0.80	13.11
grad_ascent+gd	0.10	9.18	1.6	10.6
DPO+kl	0.10	2.04	0.8	4.9
DPO+gd	0.05	8.16	0.00	11.4
NPO	0.15	13.27	1.2	14.7
NPO+kl	0.05	14.29	0.00	13.1
NPO+gd	0.10	13.27	0.00	13.1
PERMU _{tok}	0.45	2.00	0.06	17.21
PERMU	0.10	1.33	0.00	6.58

Table 10: **LLama2-7B**: Experimental Results assessing Forget Leakage, Test Retain Leakage and Model Performance for different unlearning methods. The best scores per model are highlighted, the Retain Model is not highlighted as it serves as ideal case. The results for *DPO*, *GA* and *GA+kl* are not included as the model experienced catastrophic forgetting, the *GA* models output gibberish, while *DPO* outputs it’s variants of “*I don’t know*” for any input.

Method	Autocompletion Forget ESR (%) ↓				Autocompletion Test Retain ESR (%) ↑				Model Performance ↑	
	Direct	Paraphrased	OneHop	Inverted	Direct	Paraphrased	OneHop	Inverted	Model Utility	Forget Fluency
Retain Model	0.5	0.5	1.9	1.0	99.6	98.4	55.1	42.4	0.80	3.98
PERMU _{tok}	1.1	1.3	1.9	6.0	82.6	83.2	30.6	25.3	0.74	3.81
PERMU	0.1	0.002	1.5	8.9	74.6	76.1	12.6	20	0.75	2.88
ULD	18.5	33.9	0.0	27.0	93.1	93.6	0.0	30	0.73	3.85
WHP	95.3	96.4	0.0	28.5	93.8	93.7	0.0	30	0.71	3.76
GA+gd	29.7	31.3	11.3	11.0	62.9	60.0	13.0	14	0.68	3.98
DPO+kl	60.8	60.8	11.3	17.5	80.7	75.0	20.3	25.5	0.74	3.22
DPO+gd	47.2	49.7	24.5	18.5	99.3	95.0	36.2	26.8	0.77	3.36
NPO	26.5	20.4	7.5	23.0	37.5	31.2	10	23.3	0.53	3.63
NPO+kl	66.8	71.2	15.1	32.0	74.7	79.8	23.2	33.6	0.63	3.58
NPO+gd	46.8	52.6	13.2	18.0	79.1	81.7	27.5	24.8	0.68	3.84

Figure 7: **LLama3.1-8B**: Forget Loss and Entropy of the Corrupted Logits, comparing PERMU and PERMU_{tok}, averaged from 10 runs across all training batches.

Figure 8: Distributions of PII types. (top) Length variability analysis showing median character counts and standard deviations for character length understanding; (bottom) Count of occurrences in QA's per PII type.

Figure 9: **LLama3.1-8B**:The figure compares dual objectives of unlearning and utility between PERMU and PERMU_{tok}, over increasing Forget sample proportions, i.e splits. On the upper plots, we have PII Leakage percentages for the Direct Auto-completion Attack . The lower plots show the Model Fluency, denoting the text generation quality, a metric for model performance.

F PII types and generation prompts

System Prompt for PII QA Generation

Task: Generate synthetic question-answer pairs where questions elicit personally identifiable information responses.

Input Parameters:

- `full_name`: Complete name of target user
- `user_profile`: User information profile
- `qa_config`: Target PII categories for extraction

Instructions:

1. Questions must use `full_name` and target PII categories in `qa_config`.
2. Multiple PII elements may be naturally included without explicit reference.
3. Additional non-PII context from profile enhances naturalness.
4. Strict adherence to `user_profile`, no fabrication allowed.
5. Questions must unambiguously target specific PII types.
6. ...

Output Format:

Listing 1: Expected JSON Response Structure

```

1 {
2   "question": "< question incorporating full_name and requesting PII >",
3   "answer": "< response containing the requested PII categories >"
4 }

```

Table 11: PII Generation Types and Specifications for Synthetic Data Creation. Each type follows specific generation rules to ensure realistic but synthetic personally identifiable information across different categories and regions.

PII Type	Prompt For Specific Type Generation	Example
country	Input to model, drawn from uniform distribution of 19 countries.	Denmark
fullname	Create an uncommon, synthetic full name appropriate for the specified country.	Jesper Madsen
email_address	Realistic, fake email address that aligns with the <code>full_name</code> and country	m.madsen88@libero.it
twitter_username	Fake but plausible Twitter-style username partially derived from <code>full_name</code> .	matteofarnesI_88
home_address	A realistic uncommon home address located in the specified country. Under 30 characters	Vesterbrogade 22
work_address	A realistic uncommon business address, different from the home address. Do not use business name.	Hovedgaden 44
phone_number	Format must be exactly: xxx - xxx - xxxx	207 - 456 - 7890
Occupation	"A realistic job title followed by 'at' and a fake uncommon company name (e.g., Software Engineer at Qyntari Systems)	Marketing Director at Nord-wave Solutions
DOB	Format must be exactly: dd/mm/yyyy	14/08/1975
credit_card_nr	Format must be exactly: xxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxx	4321-1234-5678-9012
bank_account_number	Random sequence of digits fewer than 18 characters.	B102938475612
bank	A realistic, uncommon, regionally plausible bank name.	Arctic Bank
bank_transaction_amount	"Amount in currency that is appropriate for the country, (e.g., \$1,529.24 for US)	DKK 12,345.00
bank_transaction_date	Realistic date that must be after the date of birth.	03/01/2021
financial_consultant_name	Realistic uncommon full name appropriate for the region.	Erik Holger Madsen
health_insurance_nr	Format: xxx-xx-xxxxx (mix of letters and numbers)	K8M-33-78901
hospital_name	Realistic, uncommon hospital name in the given country.	Nordic General Car
doctor_name	Realistic uncommon full name with 'Dr.' prefix (e.g., Dr. Mirela Kovács).	Dr. Astrid Marie Christiansen